

INSECURITY, VIGILANTISM AND POLICING IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Many African countries especially those within the Sahel region are faced with myriad of security challenges. In Nigeria problem of insecurity continues to pose very big challenge to the government; they include banditry, farmer/herders' conflict, terrorism, kidnapping, armed robbery, and cultism. The insecurity challenges facing Nigeria has overwhelmed the police force, and compelled the federal government to deploy the military to assist the police in fighting crimes. Despite the efforts of the government to strengthen the formal institutions of government to fight crimes and restore peace and safety in the country, insecurity and violent crimes persist. The study, therefore, examines the problem of insecurity, vigilantism and policing in Nigeria. The study relied on secondary sources of data, while the content analysis technique was used to analyse the secondary data. The study found that the prevalence of criminal violence in Nigeria is responsible for the formation of vigilante groups in various parts of the country. The study recommended that the government should tackle some of the socio-economic challenges that breed criminal violence and other social vices such as poverty, unemployment, inequality etc. The study also recommended licensing and training of vigilante groups so as to make them carry out their functions of apprehending criminal deviants without violating their rights.*

Keywords: *Vigilantism, insecurity, policing, crime, violent crime*

INTRODUCTION

Vigilantism is not new to human society. Since from time immemorial human beings have always looked for ways to protect themselves against petty thieves and invasion from neighbouring communities. Thus, before the concept of state police was introduced in Nigeria, many communities had conceived the idea of requesting able bodied men to volunteer to protect their communities against criminals. Vigilantism as a form of informal social control mechanism has been in existence in the US since the 1920s as a form of neighbourhood guard; they were unarmed and could arrest suspected criminals who they would hand over to the police (Amnesty International, 2008). Similarly, some form of vigilantism, such as the White Farmers, existed in South Africa around the 1910s and 1920s. However, in Nigeria today, the prevalence of vigilante is due to security challenges and violent crimes experienced in different parts of Nigeria. In some situation, the federal government had resorted to the deployment of

military officers to local communities through the formation of Joint Task Force to help fight crimes and insecurity since the police have been overwhelmed by the rate of crime in Nigeria

The increasing use of local vigilantes in the fight against crime and criminality in many local communities in Nigeria today is due to the failure of the state police to provide security for her citizens. In fact, many local residents tend to rely on local vigilantes either to report crime incident or to apprehend criminal offenders. This is because the law enforcement agencies have been stretched too thin and are becoming incapable to meet up with high rates of crime in Nigeria. Many local communities have resorted to the use of vigilantes to combat violent crimes such as armed robbery, kidnapping, homicide, car theft, terrorism, and minor crimes such as burglary, pick pocketing and even debt recovery. In some states and local government areas, vigilante groups receive approval from state police and are licensed to carry firearms. These vigilante groups, sometimes work in partnership with law enforcement agencies, particularly the police by apprehending suspected criminals and handing them over to the police, and in other situations reporting criminal suspects to the police. This symbiotic relationship between the police and local vigilantes have been able to reduce crime rates in local communities in different parts of Nigeria.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Terrorism and violent crimes are the twin problems of insecurity facing the Nigerian state today. While the government have tried various security measures including increasing police welfare, recruitment of new police officers arming the police with more sophisticated weaponry, conducting a general redeployment of officers and formation of Joint Task Forces, these measures seem not to reduce the security challenges facing the country. Of recent, the government has gone ahead to deploy military personnel to local communities so as to support the efforts of the police, but these efforts have not yielded any meaningful result; because crime rates and violent crimes continue to increase in Nigeria. To add to the problem of violent crimes, many communities are also dealing with issues of violent conflict and terrorism. In the north-east for instance, terrorism is on the increase leading to internal displacement of local residents, while in the north central there is high rates of kidnapping from terrorist for ransom, and farmer/herder conflict. Down south, the situation is not different, homicide, kidnapping especially for ransom is prevalent in the south east- and south- west, while illegal oil theft and bunkering, kidnapping, cultism, internet fraud are rampant in the south-south. A lot of these increasing crime rates are due to the debilitating economic climate in which most Nigerians are living, which have driven many people into poverty. Many adolescents now see crimes as the only way out of the hash economy since the legitimate means of livelihood appears to be limited. The law enforcement agencies have been overwhelmed by these security challenges and increasing crime rates, couple with the inept and corrupt character of some police officers that cast a doubt in the minds of the people on their ability to fight crime. As a consequence, many local communities have taken laws in to their hands

by apprehending criminals and terrorists and imposing jungle justice on them, or forming vigilante's groups to fight criminals and terrorists. This paper investigates the gap in the security architecture and crime management in Nigeria by the formal security agencies, especially the police that gave rise for the formation of vigilante groups in various communities and neighbourhoods across Nigeria.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To investigate the reasons for the prevalence of vigilante groups in Nigeria
- Ascertain whether the failure of the police to deter criminal deviance effectively is responsible for the formation of vigilante in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Data for this paper were obtained from secondary materials that were obtained from books and other online materials. The content analysis technique was used to analyze the secondary data obtained.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Vigilantism

Vigilantism is the act of preventing, investigating, punishing perceived criminal offenders without resort to legal authority. While vigilante is the person who practices in vigilantism or partake in public safety, and retributive justice without commission. In the medieval Europe, punishment of criminal deviants was exercised by secret societies known as the courts of Vehm. Johnston (1996) sees vigilante as bearing certain characteristics namely;

- (i) It involves planning and premeditation by those engaging in it;
- (ii) Its participants are private citizens whose engagement is voluntary;
- (iii) It is a form of 'autonomous citizenship' and, as such, constitutes a social movement;
- (iv) It uses or threatens the use of force;
- (v) It arises when an established order is under threat from the transgression, the potential transgression, or the imputed transgression of institutionalized norms;
- (vi) It aims to control crime or other social infractions by offering assurances (or 'guarantees') of security both to participants and to others.

Before the formation of vigilante groups, many in communities in Nigeria relied on able bodied men to carry out retributive justice as a way of punishing and deterring criminal offenders.

Nonetheless, the advent of colonial rule brought the emergence of state police that was responsible for the apprehension and prosecution of suspected criminal offenders. However, as the Nigerian economy start experiencing a downturn in the 1980s, violent crimes such as armed robbery began to increase. Apart from the dwindling economy that drives the increase in criminal behaviour, the corrupt behaviour of some law enforcement officers who collude with some criminals to escape arrest and prosecution also increase the crime rates (Akinlabi & Ihimeje, 2021). This failure of the police to fulfill their primary responsibility of fighting crime, has led to the formation of vigilante groups among local

community residents. Akinlabi & Ihimeje captured aptly the prominent role that vigilante groups are playing in local communities as they noted,

In recent years, there has been heavy reliance on community vigilante groups for security of lives and property at community levels. In some quarters, community vigilante groups have been appraised to be recording success in crime control and prevention. It is becoming a common knowledge that some communities are now engaging vigilante groups for security purposes and as an important outfit to complement the State law enforcement agencies.

Vigilante groups have played major roles in filling the gaps where the formal government security agencies have failed. For instance, in the north-east particularly in Adamawa state, hunter groups have played significant role in blocking Boko Haram from advancing and taking back cities of Gombi and Mubi axis of the state that were initially in the hands of jihadist. In the south-east, the Bakassi Boys, whose major objective was to fight crimes in Aba, Onitsha and other cities in the south-east were responsible in riding these cities of criminals. In the south-West, Amotekun has also played significant role in apprehending terrorists, kidnappers and other deviants. In the south-south, there is also the popular, OSPAC who collaborate effectively with the police in the apprehension of criminal offenders and handing over to the police (Jack-Rabin, Amalu & Abdullahi 2023). In the south-west region of Nigeria, before Omotekun was introduced as an informal security outfit to help fight crime, there was the O'odua People's Congress, while in the north there was the Sharia implementation committees or Hisba.

Interestingly, there appears to be a clear distinction between vigilante group or crime fighting in the old especially in the US and that of present-day Nigeria. In the 19th century US, vigilante groups carried out summary execution of criminals suspected to have committed homicide, whereas in today's vigilante operation, the groups such as OSPAC only apprehend and handover suspected criminal deviants to the police for prosecution. This is probably because the arrest and prosecution of criminal suspects still lies exclusively with the purview of the police. Despite the usefulness of vigilante groups in their partnership with the police in fighting crime, there are also allegations of human rights abuses, and corruption levelled against some vigilante officials.

The rise of vigilante groups in Nigeria is not unconnected with the failure of the police protect the safety and property of her citizens. The police force is overwhelmed with the magnitude of security challenges facing Nigeria today, from threat of terrorism in the north east, to farmer/herders' conflict in the north central to some parts of south east to that of IPOB and state security, including kidnapping and cult violence in the south-south. In a bid to tackle some these security challenges, the police top hierarchy introduced some reforms by adopting community policing and improving police welfare. However, irrespective of these reforms, community policing that emphasizes police and community collaboration in crime fighting does not seem to work, due to citizens' distrust of the police. Some police officers are

corrupt who connive with criminal suspects to commit crimes. In other instances, a citizen who reports crime to the police may end be a suspect of crime. As a result of the humongous security facing Nigeria today, and police inability to control and apprehend criminal suspects, many community residents have taken security into their own hands by forming vigilante groups consisting of volunteers to secure their communities and neighborhoods against suspected criminals. In some regions with ethno/religious conflict, opponents of vigilante fear that such groups could be a pawn in the hands of politicians to use against political opponents and weaker ethnic and religious groups (Crisis Group, 2022).

The Concept of Security

Security is simply the freedom from fear and danger. Security is the presence of peace, safety, happiness, and the absence from crisis (Adegbami, 2013). Security also connotes the freedom of a people to live their cherished values without threats from others. On the other hand, insecurity denotes a state of lack of safety, risk, hazards, uncertainty, lack of defence and lack of security (Daramola, 2023). The rise of vigilante group in various parts of Nigeria today is not unconnected with the high level of insecurity experienced in different parts of Nigeria today. Most community and urban dwellers have taken their security into their own hands, since government security appears to be inadequate to protect them. The government security operating through the police and other law enforcement agencies seems to have been stretched too thin with the mirage of security problems facing the country. The difficult socio-economic condition faced by many Nigerians today have driven many juveniles into criminal deviance. Increased poverty and joblessness coupled with a value system that de-emphasize hardwork as the means for achieving success, propel many frustrated youths to embrace the life of crime and criminal violence.

The Concept of Policing

The word police derived from the Greek word 'politeuin' which means to be a citizen who engages in a political activity, while polis means a city or state. Police in this regard carry out the responsibility of law enforcement and crime fighting (Johnson, 2013). Thus, the police represent the formal institution of social controls (Agwanwo, 2022). Policing also means actions taken by various institutions to regulate social relations and practices intended to secure members of community, in addition to conformity with societal norms and values (Aina, 2023).

Police, as a formal means of fighting crime and maintaining law and order was a creation of the colonialist solely for the smooth running of their colonial administration and to facilitate their economic exploitation of Nigeria (Johnson, 2013). However, before the British introduced the formal means of social control- the police force- Nigeria pre-colonial societies had informal means through which behaviours of people were regulated and social order maintained. So far, the informal means of social control that embodies the values, norms and customs of the people appears to have given way to the formal means of social control. The formal means of social control in which the police belong is not

without challenges that include poor welfare of the officers, corruption, human rights abuses, and police brutality. These challenges have decreased public trust and perception of the police, and consequently the formation of vigilante groups by citizens. Many citizens do not feel safe to entrust their security in the hands of the police, and hence the formation of vigilante groups. Vigilante groups are also not without its own deficiency just like the police. They are guilty of extra-judicial killing, human rights violations, corruption, disregard for the rule of law and murder (Aina, 2023).

Vigilantism and Policing in Nigeria

Vigilante groups can be seen in two perspectives: 1) As a community self-help policing groups with the goal of protecting the public through the law enforcement style of policing; 2) It could also be viewed or conceived as the killing of one or more people by a group of citizens without state authority or permission. This is also known as violent vigilantism. Non-state policing, on the other hand is efforts centered on the provision of security outside the coercive apparatus of the state. This form of security arrangement sees the use of both formal and informal social control mechanism to combat crime. This more like a hybrid approach to saucerization (Aina, 2023).

Theoretical Analysis of Criminal Deviance in Nigeria

Various theories have attempted to provide answers as to why individuals engage in crime and other violent behaviours. This study does not dwell on one particularly theory but attempts to draw insights from a couple of theories to help us understand why violent crimes are prevalent in Nigeria, and why the failure of the state formal means of social control has led to the formation of vigilante groups across the country. Cesera Lombroso (Igbo, 2008) in his theoretical analysis of criminal tendencies placed the problem of crime on the physical outlook of the criminals. Lombroso believed that those with mental degenerate and atavistic nature were predisposed to criminal behaviour than those without. He buttressed that criminal behaviour was inherited than socially motivated. Cohen & Felson (1979) in their routine activity theory argued that crime rates and victimization was high in areas where there was a convergence of three things: motivated offender, suitable target, and absence of a capable guardians. Felson argued that our routine activities, for instance, going out in search our daily bread, puts us in a risky position where we could become victims of crime, especially where there is absence of a capable guardian such as the police and other law enforcement agents. Edwin Sutherland (1947) in his theory of differential association argued that it is the association that produces criminal behaviour especially where the association is with individuals with negative influences. Karl Marx, rather places the blame on the economy. His analysis of society including the problem of crime is located with the economic structure of society. He argued that capitalist system has inherent class conflict due to the structure of the society that tend to favour those that controls the means of production and distribution. Marx contended that the instrument of social control such as the law and police force are put in place by the ruling class to control the oppressed class. Emile Durkheim argued that anomie in society due to

the state of normlessness is responsible for high crime incidence, but Robert Merton construed anomie slightly differently from Durkheim to explain criminal deviance. He believed that crime was due to the limited opportunity available for juveniles to access the legitimate means of achieving success goals. As a result, adolescents' resort to illegitimate means to achieve success goals. The problem of insecurity and violent crimes in Nigeria can be situated within these theories, either biological or sociological. No one single theory can exhaustively explain the crime problem in Nigeria, but a combination of them all could help us to do a detailed theoretical analysis of the crime problem in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Our findings show that the increasing use of vigilante in many rural and urban communities and neighbourhoods in Nigeria today is due to the inefficiency of the police and other law enforcement agencies. With the high level of insecurity in Nigerian, many citizens have no other choice than to seek for alternative safety measures for their lives and property. Our security agencies have been overwhelmed by the level of violent crimes in the country. Criminal violence is on the increase either from terrorism and kidnapping in the north east or banditry and farmer/herdsmen conflict in north-central. Armed robbery, kidnapping for ransom, rape, homicide, piracy are also on the increase in the south south, while in the south west, kidnapping and other violent crimes are endemic problems. Sometimes frustrated civilians take laws into their hands by inflicting instant justice on criminal offenders, but presently vigilante groups are formed in various areas who work in partnership with the police in the apprehension of criminal suspects. In addition, the study also found that the inability of law enforcement agencies especially the police to fight crimes and deter criminal offenders is responsible for the formation of vigilante groups. Due to the failure of the police to rid our society of criminal deviants, most community and urban dwellers have set up vigilante groups which have helped to provide neighborhoods a sense of security (Akinlabi & Ihimeje, 2021).

Conclusion

The increasing use of vigilante groups in Nigeria is due to the high level of insecurity experienced in different parts of Nigeria. Violent crimes are of daily occurrence in Nigeria. These violent crimes incidents include terrorism, kidnapping, armed robbery, gang violence, piracy, unlawful possession of firearms, homicide etc, The Nigerian law enforcement agencies, particularly the police appear to be too weak, inefficient and unable to combat the high rates of violent crimes. This situation is further compounded by the distrust of the police by the public, thereby making community police partnership very difficult to realize, and the harsh economic climate in which most Nigerians are living that has driven many adolescents to embrace crime, since the legitimate means of livelihood are becoming very difficult for most Nigerians. Poverty, unemployment, social inequality are on the increase daily and paving the way for most juveniles from deprived backgrounds to see criminality as the only way to survive. The security agencies appear to have been outnumbered and overwhelmed by the rate of crime,

as a result many communities have formed vigilante groups such as Omotekun in the south-west and OSPAC in the south-south region. These vigilante groups help the police by apprehending suspected criminals and handing them over to the police for prosecution. Nonetheless, vigilante groups are also not immune from crime as some of them collude with criminals to perpetrate crime. Sometimes, their high-handedness in the way they treat suspected criminal offenders raises serious concerns as to their usefulness in crime fighting and making neighbourhoods and communities safe. Some vigilante belongs to cult groups, and are heavily on drugs such as marijuana that impair their sense of reasoning and their ability to tackle crime effectively. Some vigilante groups especially in the north have been infiltrated by terrorists, while some act as informants to terrorists and kidnappers. Despite these challenges, vigilante groups are still very useful in the apprehension of suspected criminals. This will give the citizens a sense of safety and security, and reduce the tendency of people resorting to self-help in the apprehension and punishment of criminal suspects.

Recommendations

1. The government should tackle some of the socio-economic challenges that breed criminal violence in the Nigerian society, such as poverty, unemployment, inequality etc.
2. The government should recruit more police officers, including provision of adequate welfare and ammunition so that they would be able to tackle the increasing level of crimes we are currently experiencing in Nigeria. At the moment the ratio of police officers when compared to rate of criminal deviance in the country, makes the police completely inadequate to withstand the level of crime in the country.
3. The vigilante groups should be licensed by the police, trained in crime control so they can avoid human rights abuses, while apprehending suspected criminals.
4. The police should adopt a more proactive crime control techniques rather than reactive style, this may involve partnership, collaboration and building trust with citizens who will then become the eye of police in their various neighbourhoods and communities.

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